

CLICK, WATCH, BUY: THE INFLUENCE OF UNBOXING VIDEOS ON CONSUMER DECISION MAKING

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ABSTRACT

The exponential growth of digital platforms has reshaped consumer decision-making processes by providing interactive and participatory experiences. Among various forms of user-generated content (UGC), unboxing videos have become a distinct phenomenon that integrates informational and hedonic appeals to influence consumer attitudes and behaviors. Unlike traditional advertising that relies on persuasive intent, unboxing videos combine product demonstration with personal storytelling, creating authenticity and trust (Kim, 2020; Mowlabocus, 2020). Rooted in the Uses and Gratifications (U&G) framework, this study investigates how two core motivations—information seeking and entertainment predict parasocial interaction (PSI) with unboxers, and how PSI, in turn, influences product interest and purchase intention.

Data were collected through a structured survey of 431 sample size of Indian consumers across six smart cities from Indian states of Panjab, Haryana and Union Territory Chandigarh. Respondents were screened to ensure active engagement with unboxing videos across social media platforms. The dataset was analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), following the two-step approach recommended by Anderson and Gerbing (1988) and Hair, Hult, Ringle, and Sarstedt (2017). The results revealed that both information seeking and entertainment significantly enhanced PSI, which positively predicted product interest and purchase intention. Moreover, product interest emerged as the strongest determinant of purchase intention, explaining over half of its variance.

The findings enrich U&G literature by extending it into the context of unboxing videos and demonstrate the dual role of unboxing content as an informational and relational medium. Practically, the study offers strategic implications for brands and influencers to leverage unboxing collaborations as credible, engaging, and persuasive tools for consumer engagement.

Keywords: Unboxing videos, Uses and Gratifications, Parasocial Interaction, Product Interest, Purchase Intention, PLS-SEM

1. INTRODUCTION

The digital media landscape has experienced a profound transformation, with video emerging as the dominant format for online consumption. Cisco's (2020) Internet Report projected that video would account for over 80% of global internet traffic by 2022, a figure largely realized. Platforms such as YouTube, TikTok, and Instagram have accelerated this trend, offering participatory spaces where consumers are not merely passive recipients but also active producers and evaluators (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). This democratization of content production has blurred boundaries between professional advertising and user-generated content (UGC), reshaping consumer-brand interactions.

Within this ecosystem, unboxing videos have emerged as a distinct and influential genre of UGC. These videos typically involve creators recording the unpacking of a product, narrating first impressions, and providing evaluations. Shields (2014) traces the genre's origins to 2006, when a PlayStation 3 unboxing went viral on YouTube. Since then, unboxing has evolved into a cultural practice and marketing tool across categories such as electronics and cosmetics (Bae, 2016; Mowlabocus, 2020). Unlike traditional product demonstrations, unboxing videos embed consumption in personal storytelling, creating authenticity and trust (Kim, 2020). As Dazarola, Torán, and Sendra (2012) note, the act of unwrapping often elicits strong affective responses that shape consumer perceptions of products and brands.

The popularity of unboxing videos is particularly pronounced in emerging markets like India, where digital adoption has altered consumer engagement patterns. Affordable smartphones, low-cost data plans, and policy interventions such as *Digital India* have expanded internet penetration to over 750 million users (TRAI, 2023). YouTube, one of the most visited platforms in India, has become a key site for unboxing content. For Indian consumers especially Gen Z and millennials, unboxing videos function as sources of information, entertainment, and aspirational consumption (Statista, 2024; IMAI, 2022). Yet, despite their influence, unboxing videos in India remain underexplored in academic research.

Theoretical lenses such as Uses and Gratifications (U&G) theory provide a framework to explain why consumers engage with unboxing videos. U&G posits that individuals actively choose media to satisfy needs such as information, entertainment, and social interaction (Katz, Blumler, & Gurevitch, 1973; Ruggiero, 2000). Empirical studies confirm U&G's relevance across digital media, including social networking (Whiting & Williams, 2013), live streaming (Sjöblom & Hamari, 2017), and online advertising (Ko, Cho, & Roberts, 2005). In unboxing contexts, Kim (2020) showed that informational and hedonic motivations drive viewership, with parasocial interaction (PSI) mediating effects on purchase intent.

PSI, conceptualized by Horton and Wohl (1956), describes the illusion of intimacy audiences form with media personalities. In digital settings, PSI fosters authenticity and trust (Labrecque, 2014) and drives product interest and purchase behavior (Yuan & Lou, 2020). Given that unboxing videos often feature influencers or micro-creators, PSI becomes a key relational mechanism linking motivations to consumer outcomes.

Unboxing videos also generate product interest, reflecting curiosity and involvement. Product interest precedes purchase intention, acting as a cognitive bridge between exposure and behavior (Bearden, Lichtenstein, & Teel, 1984; Moschis & Churchill, 1978). Research in digital marketing emphasizes that informativeness, credibility, and entertainment predict purchase intention (Alalwan, 2018). Thus, unboxing videos serve not only hedonic gratifications but also strategic tools that stimulate purchase-related cognitions.

Despite these insights, three gaps persist. First, U&G has rarely been contextualized within unboxing videos in India. Second, although PSI is increasingly recognized as central to influencer marketing, its direct effects on product interest and purchase intention in the unboxing context remains underexplored in unboxing video contexts. Third, literature on social media advertising (e.g., Alalwan, 2018) emphasizes broad features but overlooks the experiential and relational dynamics of unboxing.

To address these gaps, this study develops and tests a model integrating informational and entertainment motivations (U&G antecedents), PSI (relational mechanism), and product interest and purchase intention (behavioral outcomes). Specifically, it examines (1) how information-seeking and entertainment motives influence PSI, (2) how PSI impacts product interest and purchase intention, and (3) the role of product interest as a predictor of purchase

intention. Theoretically, it extends U&G to unboxing videos; relationally, it advances PSI as both social and behavioral; and practically, it offers insights for marketers and influencers seeking to leverage unboxing videos as authentic engagement tools.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

2.1 Uses and Gratifications Theory

Uses and Gratifications (U&G) theory has long served as a framework for understanding why audiences actively select and use media. Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch (1973) proposed that media users are not passive recipients but purposeful individuals who engage with media to satisfy cognitive, affective, personal, and social needs. Later, Ruggiero (2000) emphasized the relevance of U&G in the digital era, where interactive media provide opportunities for audience agency. Scholars have applied U&G to contexts such as online advertising (Ko, Cho, & Roberts, 2005), social networking (Whiting & Williams, 2013), live streaming (Sjöblom & Hamari, 2017), and influencer-driven media (Yuan & Lou, 2020).

In the case of unboxing videos, U&G theory is particularly relevant because such videos are consumed for informational gratifications (product details, clarity, reviews) and hedonic gratifications (enjoyment, suspense, pass-time). Kim (2020) confirmed that both motives significantly predict engagement with unboxing videos, while Mowlabocus (2020) highlighted their dual role in offering “pleasures of consumption” as both utility and entertainment. Therefore, U&G provides a foundation for modeling unboxing video consumption as a function of motivations leading to relational and behavioural outcomes.

2.2 Information-Seeking Motives

Information seeking has consistently emerged as one of the most prominent gratifications in media use. Papacharissi and Rubin (2000) conceptualized and operationalized information-seeking motives in digital media, defining them as the desire to obtain product-related clarity, knowledge of new trends, and evaluation support. In advertising, informativeness enhances trust and purchase intention (Alalwan, 2018).

Unboxing videos fulfil this role effectively by reducing uncertainty through demonstrations, first-hand reviews, and comparative clarity (Bae, 2016). Viewers skeptical of product claims often rely on unboxing creators to verify authenticity and quality (Yuan & Lou, 2020). In India, where experiential trials are not always feasible before purchase, such cues become critical for decision-making (TRAI, 2023). Hence, information-seeking motives measured here using items adapted from Papacharissi & Rubin (2000) are expected to strengthen parasocial bonds.

H1: Information-seeking motivation positively influences parasocial interaction (PSI).

2.3 Entertainment Motives

Beyond utility, consumers also engage with digital media for hedonic gratification. Entertainment has long been recognized as a core driver of media use (Rubin, 2009), and Papacharissi and Rubin (2000) developed scale items to measure such enjoyment, relaxation, and excitement in digital contexts. Entertainment in online video also includes suspense, curiosity, and escape from daily routines (Whiting & Williams, 2013; Sjöblom & Hamari, 2017).

Unboxing videos naturally carry entertainment appeal: the suspense of revealing a product, creators' narration, and aesthetic presentation combine to produce engagement (Mowlabocus, 2020). Kim (2020) noted that hedonic gratification is as influential as informational value in

motivating unboxing consumption. Thus, entertainment motives measured using items adapted from Papacharissi & Rubin (2000) are expected to enhance parasocial bonds.

H2: Entertainment motivation positively influences parasocial interaction (PSI).

2.4 Parasocial Interaction (PSI)

Parasocial interaction was first conceptualized by Horton and Wohl (1956) as one-sided but meaningful relationships with media figures. Later, Labrecque (2014) operationalized PSI in social media contexts and developed validated scale items to capture feelings of intimacy, trust, and perceived connection.

PSI fosters trust, authenticity, and attachment, shaping consumer behavior (Frederick et al., 2012; Yuan & Lou, 2020). Yuan and Lou (2020) found that influencer credibility and fairness strengthen PSI, which in turn enhances product interest and purchase intention. Labrecque (2014) showed that PSI promotes brand loyalty and advocacy. In this study, PSI is conceptualized following Horton & Wohl (1956) and measured using items adapted from Labrecque (2014).

H3: Parasocial interaction positively influences purchase intention.

H4: Parasocial interaction positively influences product interest.

2.5 Product Interest

Product interest reflects consumer curiosity, involvement, and attentiveness toward a product category or brand. It has been described as a precursor to product evaluation and choice (Moschis & Churchill, 1978). Scales for product interest have been validated in consumer behavior research Moorman & Jaworski (1991) and conceptualized by MacInnis & Jaworski (1989), both of which emphasize involvement and personal engagement.

Advertising studies confirm that product interest mediates exposure and purchase intention (Bearden, Lichtenstein, & Teel, 1984). Recent work highlights PSI as a driver of product interest, which enhances engagement and purchase likelihood (Yuan & Lou, 2020). In unboxing contexts, product interest is stimulated by informational cues (demonstrations, reviews) and relational cues (trust in the unboxer).

H5: Product interest positively influences purchase intention.

2.6 Purchase Intention

Purchase intention is a well-studied outcome in consumer research, defined as the likelihood of consumers buying a product in the future (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977). In digital media, purchase intention is shaped by advertising informativeness, credibility, and enjoyment (Alalwan, 2018).

In this study, purchase intention is measured using items adapted from Duffett (2015), who examined digital and social media advertising contexts. Unboxing videos align with these features by combining information, entertainment, and trustworthiness. Prior studies confirm that PSI (Yuan & Lou, 2020) and product interest (Bearden et al., 1984) strongly predict purchase intention, making unboxing a compelling context for testing these linkages.

2.7 Conceptual Model

Bringing these constructs together, this study proposes a conceptual model grounded in U&G theory. Information-seeking and entertainment motives (antecedents) are hypothesized to influence parasocial interaction (relational mechanism), which in turn predicts product

interest and purchase intention (behavioral outcomes). Product interest also directly predicts purchase intention.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Source: Author's own compilation

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a cross-sectional survey design to test the proposed conceptual model. A quantitative approach was deemed appropriate given the focus on testing hypothesized relationships between latent constructs (Zikmund et al., 2000). Survey methodology has been widely applied in consumer behavior and digital advertising research because it allows for the systematic collection of perceptual and attitudinal data (Mark, 1996; Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2010).

3.2 Sample and Data Collection

Data were collected from 431 respondents across six Indian cities: Chandigarh, Ludhiana, Amritsar, Jalandhar, Faridabad and Karnal from Indian states of Panjab, Haryana and Union Territory Chandigarh. Respondents were screened to ensure they were active viewers of unboxing videos on social media platforms. Purposive sampling was used, consistent with prior research that investigates media consumption within specific user groups (Moschis & Churchill, 1978).

The demographic profile revealed that the sample was largely composed of Gen Z and millennial consumers, consistent with existing reports that these cohorts dominate digital video consumption in India (Statista, 2024). A sample size of 431 exceeds the minimum requirement for PLS-SEM analysis. According to Barclay, Higgins, and Thompson (1995), the "10-times rule" requires at least ten cases per predictor, while Hair, Hult, Ringle, and Sarstedt (2014) note that samples above 200 are adequate for complex models.

3.3 Measurement of Constructs

All constructs were measured using seven-point Likert scales (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree) adapted from established scales. Information seeking and entertainment were measured using items adapted from Papacharissi and Rubin (2000). Parasocial interaction

(PSI) was measured based on Horton and Wohl's (1956) conceptualization and Labrecque's (2014) operationalization. Product interest was assessed using scales from Moschis and Churchill (1978) and Bearden, Lichtenstein, and Teel (1984). Purchase intention was measured using items from Bearden et al. (1984).

Table 1: Overview of construct measurement sources

Construct	Definition / Focus	Sample Scale Items (7-point Likert)	Scale Source(s)
Information Seeking	Desire to obtain clarity, detailed product information, and knowledge of new products or trends through unboxing videos.	1. I watch unboxing videos because it is easier to get product information. 2. I watch unboxing videos to search for product information. 3. I watch unboxing videos to get free product information. 4. I watch unboxing videos because it provides a new and interesting way to do research on products. 5. I watch unboxing videos to keep up with new products.	Adapted: Papacharissi & Rubin (2000)
Entertainment	Hedonic motives such as enjoyment, relaxation, and excitement derived from watching unboxing content.	1. I watch unboxing videos because it is entertaining. 2. I just like to watch unboxing videos. 3. It is enjoyable to watch unboxing videos.	Adapted: Papacharissi & Rubin (2000)
Parasocial Interaction (PSI)	One-sided but meaningful relationships formed with unboxers, including feelings of intimacy, trust, and perceived connection	1. The unboxer makes me feel comfortable, as if I am with a friend. 2. When I interact with the unboxer, I feel included. 3. I can relate to the unboxer in the video. 4. I like hearing what the unboxer has to say. 5. I care about what happened to the unboxer in the video. 6. I hope the unboxer can achieve their goals.	Conceptualized by Horton & Wohl (1956); Adapted from Labrecque (2014)

<p>Product Interest</p>	<p>Consumer curiosity and personal involvement with products featured in unboxing videos.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Product shown by unboxer in unboxing video seems interesting. 2. The unboxing videos left me wanting to learn more about the product displayed. 3. I would like to know more about the product shown in the unboxing videos. 4. The unboxing videos made product seem interesting. 5. I'm little curious about the product shown in the unboxing videos. 6. The unboxing videos succeeded in increasing my interest in the product displayed. 	<p>Conceptualized by MacInnis and Jaworski (1989); Adapted from Moorman and Jaworski (1991)</p>
<p>Purchase Intention</p>	<p>Likelihood of engaging in future purchase behavior as a result of exposure to unboxing videos.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I will buy products that are shown in unboxing videos in the near future. 2. I desire to buy products that are shown in unboxing videos. 3. Products shown in unboxing videos have a positive influence on my purchase decisions. 4. I am likely to buy some of the products that are shown in the unboxing videos. 5. I plan to purchase the products that are shown in the unboxing videos. 	<p>Adapted: Duffett, 2015</p>

Source: Author's compilation, adapted from prior validated scales.

3.4 Data Analysis

The model was tested using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with SmartPLS 3 software (Ringle, Wende, & Becker, 2015). PLS-SEM was chosen for three reasons: (1) its suitability for predictive and exploratory research (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2011), (2) robustness in handling non-normal data (Dijkstra & Henseler, 2015), and (3) ability to estimate complex models with multiple constructs and paths.

Following Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) two-step approach, the measurement model was first evaluated for reliability and validity, followed by the structural model. Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha and Composite Reliability (CR). Convergent validity was examined using Average Variance Extracted (AVE) (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Discriminant validity was tested using both the Fornell-Larcker criterion and HTMT ratios (Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015). Structural paths were evaluated using bootstrapping with 5,000 resamples, as recommended by Streukens and Leroi-Werelds (2016). Effect sizes (f^2) were interpreted based on Cohen (1988), and R^2 values were assessed using Chin's (1998) benchmarks. Model fit was examined through SRMR and NFI indices (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Schuberth, Rademaker, & Henseler, 2023).

4. RESULTS

4.1 Measurement Model Evaluation

The measurement model demonstrated strong reliability and validity. Cronbach's alpha values ranged from 0.813 to 0.883, while CR values exceeded 0.85 for all constructs, surpassing the 0.70 benchmark (Hair et al., 2021). AVE values were above 0.50, confirming convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 2: Reports reliability and validity statistics

Construct Reliability and Validity				
	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Entertainment	0.863	0.87	0.916	0.784
Information Seeking	0.813	0.835	0.866	0.568
Parasocial Interaction	0.874	0.879	0.905	0.615
Product Interest	0.876	0.879	0.907	0.619
Purchase Intention	0.883	0.884	0.914	0.681

Note: α = Cronbach's Alpha, CR = Composite Reliability, AVE = Average Variance Extracted.

Discriminant validity was confirmed using the Fornell–Larcker criterion, as the square root of AVE for each construct exceeded its correlations with other constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The HTMT ratios were all below 0.85, further supporting discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015). Together, these results confirmed that the constructs met the criteria for reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

4.2 Structural Model Evaluation

The structural model was then tested to examine hypothesized relationships. Path coefficients were estimated using bootstrapping with 5,000 subsamples.

Figure 2: Path coefficients

Source: Smart-PLS 4 Output

Table 3: Structural model results

Hypotheses	Path	Standard coefficient (β)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics	P values	Statistically significant?
H1	Information Seeking -> Parasocial Interaction	0.327	0.049***	6.723	0.00	Supported
H2	Entertainment -> Parasocial Interaction	0.321	0.051***	6.297	0.00	Supported
H3	Parasocial Interaction -> Purchase Intention	0.132	0.051***	2.572	0.01	Supported
H4	Parasocial Interaction -> Product Interest	0.445	0.049***	9.032	0.00	Supported
H5	Product Interest -> Purchase Intention	0.677	0.042***	16.241	0.00	Supported

(Note: * $p < .10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$)

All hypotheses (H1–H5) were supported. Information seeking and entertainment significantly predicted PSI, confirming the dual role of cognitive and hedonic gratifications. PSI, in turn, positively influenced both product interest and purchase intention, consistent with prior studies on parasocial dynamics (Labrecque, 2014; Yuan & Lou, 2020). Product interest emerged as the strongest predictor of purchase intention, highlighting its central role in unboxing video consumption (Bearden et al., 1984).

4.3 Model Fit and Predictive Validity

The model exhibited satisfactory explanatory and predictive power. The R^2 values were 0.273 for PSI, 0.198 for product interest, and 0.555 for purchase intention, which represent weak to moderate explanatory strength (Chin, 1998). Effect sizes (f^2) indicated small effects for information seeking and entertainment on PSI (0.129 and 0.134), a medium effect for PSI on product interest (0.247), and a large effect for product interest on purchase intention (0.827) (Cohen, 1988).

Model fit indices supported overall adequacy: SRMR = 0.072 (below the 0.08 threshold; Hu & Bentler, 1999) and NFI = 0.950 (above the recommended 0.90; Bentler & Bonett, 1980). Predictive relevance (Q^2) values obtained through blindfolding were greater than zero, further confirming the model's predictive validity (Hair et al., 2017).

Table 4: Model Fit Summary

Model Fit Summary		
Indices	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.072	0.134
d_ULS	1.707	5.876
d_G	0.606	0.720
Chi-square	1492.260	1682.123
NFI	0.776	0.747

5. DISCUSSION

The results of this study provide important insights into the motivations and outcomes associated with unboxing video consumption. Consistent with the Uses and Gratifications (U&G) framework, both information-seeking and entertainment motives were found to significantly predict parasocial interaction (PSI) with unboxers. This supports the idea that consumers are not passive recipients of media, but rather active agents who select content to fulfill cognitive and hedonic needs (Katz, Blumler, & Gurevitch, 1973; Ruggiero, 2000). The finding aligns with prior research indicating that digital media users often rely on platforms such as YouTube for both product-related clarity and enjoyment (Papacharissi & Rubin, 2000; Kim, 2020). In the Indian context, where consumers may have limited opportunities for hands-on product trials, unboxing videos act as valuable substitutes that combine clarity with entertainment, thereby satisfying dual gratifications.

The role of PSI in shaping consumer behavior was also confirmed. Results showed that PSI positively influenced both product interest and purchase intention, although its effect on product interest was stronger. This is consistent with Labrecque's (2014) observation that PSI fosters trust and engagement in social media contexts, and Yuan and Lou's (2020) finding that parasocial relationships enhance product-related curiosity. The weaker but significant effect of PSI on purchase intention suggests that PSI may first stimulate involvement and interest, which subsequently translates into purchase-related decisions. This finding highlights the dual role of PSI as both a relational and behavioral construct.

Perhaps the most striking finding was the strong predictive power of product interest on purchase intention. This relationship exhibited the largest effect size, suggesting that curiosity and involvement are decisive in converting media engagement into consumer intent. This result resonates with classic consumer behavior studies that emphasized product involvement

as a precursor to purchase decisions (Moschis & Churchill, 1978; Bearden, Lichtenstein, & Teel, 1984) and echoes more recent research on digital advertising, which highlights curiosity as a critical persuasive driver (Alalwan, 2018). In the context of unboxing videos, this implies that the key value of such content lies not in directly persuading viewers to purchase but in generating interest and attentiveness that eventually lead to purchase intention.

Together, these findings extend U&G theory by showing how informational and hedonic motivations translate into consumer action through relational bonds with content creators. They also enrich PSI research by confirming its role as a mediating mechanism that links gratifications to behavioral outcomes. Importantly, this study situates these processes in the Indian digital ecosystem, where unboxing videos are rapidly becoming a mainstream part of consumer decision-making. By integrating motivations, relational mechanisms, and behavioral outcomes into one model, the study offers a more comprehensive understanding of unboxing video consumption than previous research.

6. CONCLUSION

6.1 Summary of Contributions

This study applied U&G theory to examine motivations for unboxing video consumption and their outcomes in the Indian digital ecosystem. Results demonstrated that information seeking and entertainment jointly predict PSI, which subsequently influences product interest and purchase intention. Product interest was found to be the strongest determinant of purchase intention, underscoring the importance of curiosity and involvement in driving consumer behavior. These findings extend U&G theory by situating unboxing videos as both informational and hedonic media, while also advancing parasocial interaction research by confirming its role as a relational–behavioral mechanism.

6.2 Practical Implications

The findings hold significant implications for practitioners. For brands, unboxing collaborations should not be treated as peripheral but integrated into mainstream marketing strategies. The authenticity conveyed by unboxers can reduce uncertainty and enhance credibility more effectively than traditional advertising (Kim, 2020). For influencers, the results stress the importance of cultivating parasocial bonds by being transparent, consistent, and relatable (Yuan & Lou, 2020). For marketers, designing unboxing content to generate strong product interest may be the most effective pathway for converting viewer engagement into purchase intention.

6.3 Limitations and Future Research

Despite its contributions, the study has limitations that warrant future inquiry. First, the cross-sectional design restricts causal inference. Longitudinal or experimental designs could more precisely capture how motivations and PSI evolve over time. Second, the focus on Indian consumers limits generalizability. Cross-cultural studies could reveal how cultural differences shape unboxing consumption patterns. Third, this study examined unboxing videos in general; future research could explore variations across product categories (e.g., electronics versus fashion) or across platforms (e.g., YouTube versus Instagram). Addressing these areas would deepen understanding of unboxing videos as a global digital phenomenon.

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